

IRISCC

D8.2

Optimised IRISCC VA Management System

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Abstract

Key words

Virtual Access, Catalogue of services, Statistics, Management

This report describes the Virtual Access (VA) management system to be implemented in the IRISCC project, both in terms of the tools to be proposed and the relationships between the various project tasks involved. In particular, it describes the link with the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS) and the monitoring of usage of VA services.

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface. API is a way for two or more computer programs or components to communicate with each other.
CoS	Catalogue of Services, see ISIA.
ISIA	Platform hosted at CNRS to share data, information and resources such as service catalogues of various research infrastructures.
KPI	Key Performance Indicator, a quantifiable metric that uses data to measure the effectiveness of an action or objective.
Matomo	The most common free and open-source web analytics application to track online visits to one or more websites and display reports on these visits for analysis.
Metadata schema	The metadata schema lists the data elements with their definitions. In addition, it states the rules that govern the use of each specific data elements to describe a resource.
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSO	Single Sign-On
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Project's Work Package

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Executive summary

IRISCC Virtual Access (VA) provides free and unrestricted online access to services and resources related to climate change risks. Work Package 8 (WP8) aims to implement a centralized and harmonized system for managing user access. VA management will be centrally coordinated to implement and ensure a uniform, standard service provision and interface to the IRISCC services for users, following the harmonized access practices and policies established in Task T6.1. The entire VA process is managed by T8.2 and will serve as a bridge between the Catalogue of services (T7.2) and access provision to the VA services (WP9).

All VA services are listed and fully described in the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS), the single reference for users. These services will be accessed through the respective RI data centres. The VA system automatically retrieves metadata from the CoS via the ISIA Application Programming Interface (API) and provides a user-friendly VA interface. No additional input from service providers is required. The VA portal is accessible from the IRISCC website or directly using this URL: <https://aeris-services.ipsl.fr/iriscc-va.html>.

The VA system includes a dashboard for service usage tracking and reporting. Metrics will be collected via visit counters, API calls, and manual or automated reporting. Each service is expected to submit usage data (start date, end date, user info, results) through a dedicated API. This data feeds into annual usage reports (WP9) and helps assess service relevance and impact. Most VA services are open-access and available via RI portals. Registration may be required for advanced features or usage tracking. Open access means for most services we will only get quantitative metrics (number of accesses, etc.) not detailed info about users (email, etc.).

1. Overview of IRISCC VA Management

Virtual Access (VA) enables users to access services provided by a facility or infrastructure through communication networks. This is achieved through web-based platforms, virtualisation technologies, and secure network connections. In most cases, VA is free. An unlimited number of users can simultaneously use the available services or resources, and the users are not selected. Virtual access within IRISCC concerns access to scientific data, digital tools and/or integrated online services related to climate change risks.

IRISCC Work Package (WP) 8's overall objective is to support and operate efficient, harmonised, and centralised management of user access to the established IRISCC services on climate change related risks. In particular, Task T8.2 will implement and operate the centralised Virtual Access management system. The expected outcome is the delivery of a coherent and efficient operational access management system capitalising on the different Research Infrastructures' (RIs') expertise and knowledge. It will ensure adequate and satisfactory user access to climate change risk services through effective cross-RI collaboration.

VA management will be centrally coordinated to implement and ensure a uniform, standard service provision and interface to the IRISCC services for users, following the harmonised access practices and policies established in Task T6.1. The entire VA process is managed by T8.2 and will serve as a bridge between the Catalogue of services (T7.2) and access provision to the VA services (WP9). Figure 1 shows the links between WP7 (Discovery), WP8 (Management) and WP9 (Access).

T8.2 will monitor the onboarding of the VA services in the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS) utilising the specific RI information from T9.1. VA services will be made available through the CoS. and are also available via their respective RI's data centre to ensure long term access and sustainability.

Task 8.2 will also collect some usage statistics to help Task 8.4 (access provision monitoring and evaluation) and WP9 with their reporting. Over the course of the project, all services offered through CoS will have a basic set of metrics implemented. The statistics collected by the VA management system will be aligned with KPIs to be defined with Task 8.4.

Figure 1. Overview of the IRISCC Virtual Access (VA) Management System.

2. Description of services in the VA management system

The IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS) is the main reference for the users and the single source of consistent information on all operational services on climate change-related risks and vulnerabilities made available to users in the IRISCC project via transnational and virtual access.

All VA services will be described and made discoverable through the CoS. Services will be accessible at the respective RI's data centres, for long term access and sustainability. WP9 is leading the onboarding of services (see IRISCC Deliverable D9.1 [R3] for a description of the services). To retrieve these metadata, the VA management system will use the API provided by ISIA (<https://api.isia.cnrs.fr/api/>). A cache of this information will be stored in the system and regularly updated. It will allow an integrated, user-friendly VA page with a list of VA services and associated tools (statistics, etc.) requests^[OBI] ^[OBI] will be sent to the CoS developers to improve and facilitate the harvesting.

The VA system will only use information from the CoS and no additional input will be requested from service providers. All VA services need to be fully described in the CoS. Tables Table 1 and Table 2 lists the information that the VA system retrieves from the CoS. All these fields are mandatory (see IRISCC Deliverable D7.1 [R1] for a complete description of the CoS metadata schema). The VA management system uses the identifiers (see field "ID" in Table 1) provided by the CoS to uniquely identify services and service providers.

Table 1: Service providers' description that IRISCC VA system retrieves from the CoS.

Providers metadata		
Field name	Definition	Type
ID	A persistent identifier, a unique reference to the Provider (as provided by ISIA)	String
Name	Full Name of the Provider/Organisation offering the resource and acting as the main contact point	String
Description	A high-level description of the Provider in non-technical terms, with the vision, mission, objectives, background, experience	String
Logo	Link (URL) to the logo/visual identity of the Provider	URL
Webpage	The website with information about the Provider	URL
Institutions	Name of the organisations/institutions hosting the Provider	String

Table 2: Service description that IRISCC VA system retrieves from the CoS.

Services metadata		
Field name	Description	Type
ID	A persistent identifier, a unique reference to the Service/Resource (as provided by ISIA)	String
Name	Service/Resource Full Name as assigned by the Provider	String
Description	A general description in non-technical terms of what the Service/Resource does, the functionality it provides and Service/Resources it enables to access	String
Logo	Link to the logo/visual identity of the Resource. If there is no specific logo for the Resource the logo of the Provider may be used.	URL
Webpage	Webpage with information about the Service/Resource usually hosted and maintained by the Provider	URL
Provider ID	Id of the service provider (see Table 1)	String
Main image	This image will appear at the top of the description sheet and will be representative of the service.	URL
Contact	Main contact of the service	Email
Data policy	Information about the access policies that apply (when relevant)	URL
Tags	Keywords associated to the Service	String

3. Provision and access

Most of VA services are open access (no authentication needed) and already available via RI portals (IRISCC CoS is not necessarily the single-entry point). When needed, authentication and authorization of the users will be managed at the VA services provider's level. However, the providers may deploy the federated AAI service, where it's feasible and needed as defined in T6.1. Users will register, accept the terms and conditions of the VA services.

The provision of VA is free-of-charge to users and openly available. But it may not be in some cases, for example for certain data curation requests or processing requiring

significant computing resources. Registration may also be required by service providers to be able to track the use of their services and to contact users to ask for feedback, or to access advanced features.

The VA management system is connected to the Data Terra/AERIS SSO (Single Sign-On). Based on Keycloak, it will allow users to authenticate using their institutional credentials (Edugain federation) or their ORCID. ENVRI ID and Egi-Check-In may be added in the near future, as the Data Terra/AERIS SSO system plans to implement the AARC blueprint architecture. This will ensure compliance with the recommendations from WP6 (see IRISCC D6.1 Landscape analysis of AAI at RIs and cookbook for connecting to the AAI federation, R2).

In the VA portal, different user roles will be defined:

- user: sees list of services, one user is defined by one IP address, use of VA portal is tracked
- Service admin: report usage and see access metrics only for one service
- Admin: access all data

4. VA Statistics

The VA management system shall provide a dashboard to monitor the provision of services and their use. This is, in particular, to be able to report the actual use (i.e. not just a visit to the CoS or the site hosting the service) of the RI's VA services via the IRISCC Management system. VA management system thus provides a simple way for service providers to report the usage (manually or automatically).

IRISCC VA management system implements basic user tracking, such as IP address logging or visit counters. These can help generate consistent usage statistics (visits, downloads, and requests) without requiring user registration. Each VA service should implement additional tracking tailored to the nature of the service—for example, tracking downloads of available products, logging model requests that result in new product generation, or monitoring API usage. Uniform display and interpretation of such statistics across services will improve reporting and comparability. Service providers should also do their utmost to ensure that access is not granted to users falling under restrictive measures from the EU, using access filters where feasible.

A challenge that drives from the open access is that for most services we will only get quantitative metrics (number of accesses, etc.) not detailed info about users (email, etc.). Statistics on the use of the IRISCC online services can be tracked in several ways:

- Visits to the CoS
- Visits to the VA management system (using Matomo)
- Access to the different services through the VA portal is tracked by counting hits on the corresponding button
- Effective usage of the services as recorded by each service (API)

Access statistics will be stored in a central database. Each time a service is used, a service will post the information described in Table Table 3: VA Application API payload. using an API. This can be done for example:

- once after the user request is completed or
- in two steps (for example registering first *startDate*, *infoUrl*, *user* and *service* and then, once completed, adding the *endDate* and the *resultUrl*).

To access the API, service providers will need a token, obtained from the login and password of an AERIS keycloak account. Code examples will be provided to service providers.

In addition to storing basic user statistics, we will develop a framework that allows each service provider to provide more detailed contextual information to be used in the annual WP9 reports. Metrics such as the amount of data downloaded, the time users spend on the service, and the number of requests made can offer valuable insights into the relevance and impact of each service. By enabling providers to interpret and explain these metrics, we aim to support a more meaningful assessment of service usage and importance that could be provided each year.

Table 3: VA Application API payload.

Application (= use of a service by a user)			
Field name	Definition	Type	Required
startDate	Example: 2023-02-13T10:00:00.000Z	Date	Mandatory
endDate		Date	Optional
service	Identifier of the service (see Table 2)	String	Mandatory
user	Email of the user who accessed the service	Email	Optional
IP	Internet Protocol	IP	Optional
infoUrl	URL of an information page: status of the request, etc	URL	Optional
resultUrl	Link to the result: landing page of the dataset in the portal, processing result, etc.	URL	Optional
comment		URL	Optional
Additional metrics	KPIs to be defined with Task 8.4	Array	Optional

5. References

Reference	
No	Description/Link
R1	IRISCC Deliverable D7.1 – Definition of requirements for proposed design for IRISCC Catalogue of Services. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13354103
R2	IRISCC Deliverable D6.1 – Landscape analysis of AAI at RIs and cookbook for connecting to the AAI federation. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13375310
R3	IRISCC Deliverable D9.1 – Report defining and describing R1 services. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo